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Time-Dependent Hazard Modelling of Breast Cancer Survival: An Extended Cox Framework with Proportional Hazards Assessment

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Abstract

Objectives: To investigate the proportional hazards' assumption in breast cancer survival analysis. Also to build a more flexible version of the Cox regression model that brings in time-dependent covariates, aiming for sharper hazard estimates. **Method:** A retrospective analysis was conducted using a publicly available dataset comprising 272 breast cancer patients with long-term follow-up. Descriptive statistics, Kaplan-Meier estimation, and multivariable Cox proportional hazards modeling were applied. The proportional hazards assumption was examined through time-dependent covariate interactions. An extended Cox model was subsequently formulated, and model performance was assessed using -2 log-likelihood, Akaike Information Criterion, and likelihood ratio statistics. **Findings:** Out of all patients, 77 (28.3%) events were observed during the study period. Tumor grade was identified as a significant predictor of survival (HR = 2.382; 95% CI 1.653-3.433). The proportional hazards assumption was violated for age ($p < 0.001$) and tumor diameter ($p = 0.001$), indicating the presence of time-dependent effects. The extended Cox model demonstrated a substantial improvement in fit, with -2 log-likelihood decreasing from 760.128 to 326.791 and AIC from 772.128 to 344.791, confirming enhanced explanatory performance. The findings confirm that incorporating time-dependent covariates improves model adequacy and provides a more reliable and realistic framework for breast cancer survival analysis, particularly in the presence of non-proportional hazards. **Novelty:** This study presents an integrated modeling approach that combines proportional hazards assessment with a time-dependent Cox regression model. By addressing violations of model assumptions while preserving interpretability, the proposed framework provides a practical and methodologically robust alternative to conventional survival models.

Keywords: Breast cancer; Survival analysis; Cox proportional hazards; Time-dependent covariates; Non-proportional hazards; Hazard modeling

1 Introduction

Breast cancer is still one of the most common causes of cancer death worldwide, which makes survival analysis important. Survival analysis methods are widely used to evaluate time-to-event outcomes and identify prognostic factors influencing patient survival. Publicly available clinical datasets have facilitated such analyses by providing reliable longitudinal data for model development and validation⁽¹⁾. Among these, the Cox proportional hazard model is one of the most applied techniques due to its semi-parametric formulation and ability to estimate hazard ratio without specifying the baseline hazard function^{(2), (3)}.

However, the Cox model is based on the proportional hazards (PH) assumption, which requires that the effect of a covariate remains constant over time. In real-world clinical data, particularly in breast cancer studies, this assumption is frequently violated as risk factors often exhibit time-dependent behavior. Ignoring such violations may lead to biased estimates and incorrect conclusions. Consequently, recent methodological advancements have focused on extending the Cox model to incorporate time-dependent covariates and dynamic hazard structures, thereby improving model flexibility and accuracy.

Furthermore, although extended Cox models and alternative approaches such as restricted mean survival time have been proposed, there remains a need for a comprehensive framework that integrates assumption testing, model extension, and performance validation within a unified analytical structure^{(2), (3), (4), (5)}. Such an approach is essential for accurately capturing the dynamic nature of survival risk.

Recent studies in breast cancer survival analysis have highlighted the importance of incorporating patient heterogeneity, treatment effects, and tumor characteristics into survival models^{(6), (7), (8), (9)}. These studies suggest that factors such as tumor grade, tumor size, and treatment modalities significantly influence survival outcomes, often in a time-dependent manner. Nevertheless, many existing analyses continue to rely on the classical Cox model without adequately testing or addressing violations of the PH assumption.

In addition to classical statistical approaches, machine learning-based survival models, including random survival forests and neural network-based methods, have been increasingly applied to capture complex relationships in survival data^{(10), (11), (12)}. While these models often demonstrate improved predictive performance, their lack of interpretability limits their applicability in clinical decision-making, where understanding the influence of individual covariates is essential.

Recent developments in stochastic modeling of cancer progression provide additional insights into the temporal evolution of disease and uncertainty in survival outcomes^{(13), (14)}. These approaches emphasize the importance of incorporating probabilistic dynamics into survival analysis to better reflect real-world disease processes.

So, in this paper, we test the proportional hazards assumption with real breast cancer data, then develop and compare an extended Cox model with time-dependent covariates. The idea is to show just how much can improve analysis by letting covariate effects move with time.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study Design and Data Source

NKI Breast cancer data sets Mendeley Data (DOI: 10.17632/2y5nr64gc2.1)⁽¹⁾ were used to do a retrospective secondary data analysis. The dataset includes 272 patients, all with long-term follow-up data. The primary outcome assessed was overall survival time—basically, how many years passed from each patient’s diagnosis to either their death or the last time they were checked on (if they were still alive).

2.2 Data Quality Control and Preprocessing

The dataset underwent thorough cleaning and preprocessing to ensure accurate and consistent analysis. Records with invalid survival times (≤ 0) or inconsistent event coding were removed from the analysis. Missing values in continuous variables were handled using mean imputation. The proportion of missing data was minimal (less than 5%). Variables with more than 20% missing values were excluded to maintain data quality. Outliers were identified using standardized z-scores and boxplot methods. Observations with absolute z-scores greater than 3 were examined and retained only if clinically relevant. Binary variables, such as chemotherapy and hormonal therapy, were coded as 0 (No) and 1 (Yes). Ordinal variables, including tumor grade, were retained in their original form.

2.3 Survival Function and Hazard Function

Let T denote survival time. The survival function is defined as

$$S(t) = P(T > t)$$

The hazard function is

$$h(t) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{P(t \leq T < t + \Delta t | T \geq t)}{\Delta t}$$

The relationship between survival and hazard is

$$S(t) = \exp\left(-\int_0^t h(u)du\right)$$

2.4 Classical Cox Proportional Hazard Model

The Cox model specifies the hazard as

$$h(t;X) = h_0(t) \exp(\beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_p X_p)$$

Where

$h_0(t)$ is the baseline hazard function, X_i are covariates, β_i are regression coefficients
The model assumes proportional hazards.

$$\frac{h(t;X_i)}{h(t;X_j)} = \exp(\beta(X_i - X_j))$$

Which is constant over time.

2.5 Partial Likelihood Estimation

Cox regression parameters were estimated using the partial likelihood

$$L(\beta) = \prod_{i=1}^D \frac{\exp(\beta X_i)}{\sum_{j \in R(t_i)} \exp(\beta X_j)}$$

Here,

D is number of observed events, $R(t_i)$ is risk set at time (t_i)

2.6 Baseline Hazard Estimation

The cumulative baseline hazard was estimated using the Breslow estimator

$$H_0(t) = \sum_{t_i \leq t} \frac{1}{\sum_{j \in R(t_i)} \exp(\beta X_j)}$$

The survival function becomes $S(t \setminus X) = \exp[H_0(t) \exp(\beta X)]$

2.7 Assessment of Proportional Hazards Assumption

To evaluate proportionality, time-dependent covariates interactions were introduced using log-transformed time $Z_i(t) = X_i \cdot \log(t)$

The extended hazard model becomes $h(t \setminus X) = h_0(t) \exp(\beta X + \gamma X \log(t))$

If $\gamma \neq 0$, the hazard ratio value varies over time, indicating violation of proportional hazards. Statistical significance of interaction terms was assessed at $\alpha = 0.05$.

2.8 Model Adequacy and Comparison

Model performance was evaluated using

- -2 log likelihood
- Likelihood Ratio test
- Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)

AIC was computed as $AIC = -2l(\beta) + 2k$

Where k denotes number of model parameters. And AIC indicates superior model fit.

2.9 Software Implementation

All the analyses were done using the IBM SPSS 27 version statistical program, and the Cox regression module was employed. The Kaplan Meier estimation, proportional hazards testing using time-dependent covariates, and model comparisons using the likelihood ratio test were all done in the survival analysis module.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Descriptive Analysis

The baseline characteristics of the study population are presented in Table 1. There were a total of 272 breast cancer patients in the analysis. Out of the total number of breast cancer patients, 77 (28.3%) experienced the event (death), whereas 195 (71.7%) patients were censored during the follow-up. The mean age of breast cancer patients was 44.05 ± 5.47 years. The average diameter of the tumors for breast cancer patients was 22.53 ± 8.70 mm. The average number of positive lymph nodes for breast cancer patients was 1.34 ± 2.11 . About 39.3% of breast cancer patients received chemotherapy, whereas 13.2% received hormonal therapy.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Study Population (n = 272)

Variable	Mean \pm SD/%	Min	Max
Age (years)	44.05 \pm 5.47	26	53
Tumor Diameter (mm)	22.53 \pm 8.70	2	50
Positive Nodes	1.34 \pm 2.11	0	13
Tumor Grade	2.13 \pm 0.80	1	3
Chemotherapy	107 (39.3%)	–	–
Hormonal Therapy	36 (13.2%)	–	–
Death Event	77 (28.3%)	–	–

3.2 Kaplan–Meier Survival Analysis

The Kaplan–Meier survival curve is shown in Figure 1. The mean overall survival time was 13.72 years (95% CI: 12.84–14.60). The survival curve demonstrates gradual decline with approximately 60% survival probability at 14.36 years. This confirms long-term follow-up adequacy for hazard modelling. The Kaplan–Meier survival curve is shown in Figure 1.

3.3 Classical Cox Proportional Hazards Model

The classical Cox model demonstrated significant overall model fit. The results of the classical Cox regression model are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Classical Cox Regression Results

Variable	β	SE	Wald	p-value	HR	95% CI
Age	0.043	0.033	1.75	0.186	1.044	0.980–1.113
Chemotherapy	0.327	0.244	1.79	0.181	1.387	0.859–2.239
Hormonal	0.131	0.313	0.18	0.675	1.14	0.617–2.108
Diameter	0.02	0.017	1.36	0.244	1.02	0.986–1.056
Positive Nodes	0.078	0.064	1.47	0.226	1.081	0.953–1.226
Grade	0.868	0.187	21.53	<0.001	2.382	1.653–3.433

Tumor grade was the only statistically significant predictor. Each one-unit increase in grade increased mortality risk by 138%. However, proportional hazards assumption requires validation.

3.4 Proportional Hazards Assumption Testing

Time-dependent covariate interactions were introduced. The time-dependent interaction effects are summarized in Table 3.

Fig 1. Kaplan–Meier survival curve

Table 3. Time-Dependent Interaction Effects

Interaction Term	β	SE	p-value
age \times log(time)	-0.389	0.098	<0.001
diameter \times log(time)	-0.148	0.044	0.001
posnodes \times log(time)	-0.035	0.065	0.59

Significant interaction effects for age and tumor diameter indicate violation of the proportional hazards assumption. Therefore, the classical Cox model does not fully capture time-varying risk dynamics.

3.5 Extended Time-Dependent Model Performance

The extended model demonstrated substantial improvement. Model comparison between classical and extended Cox models is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Model Comparison

Metric	Classical Model	Extended Model
-2 Log Likelihood	760.128	326.791
AIC	772.128	344.791
LR X^2	47.247	484.584
p-value	<0.001	<0.001

The extended model exhibits drastically reduced AIC and improved likelihood ratio statistics, confirming superior explanatory performance.

3.6 Discussion

This study evaluated the applicability of the Cox proportional hazards model in breast cancer survival analysis and highlighted the importance of incorporating time-dependent covariates when the proportional hazards (PH) assumption is violated. Although the classical Cox model demonstrated statistical significance (LR $X^2 = 47.247$, $p < 0.001$), the PH assumption was not satisfied for key variables such as age and tumor diameter, indicating the presence of time-varying effects.

These findings are consistent with recent methodological research emphasizing the limitations of the traditional Cox model under non-proportional hazards conditions. Studies have shown that ignoring time-dependent effects may lead to biased estimation and reduced model reliability. Advancements in time-varying Cox models demonstrate that incorporating temporal interactions significantly improves model flexibility and inference accuracy in clinical survival data^{(3), (5)}.

The extended Cox model incorporating time-dependent covariate interactions demonstrated a substantial improvement in model performance. The reduction in -2 log-likelihood from 760.128 to 326.791 and the decrease in AIC from 772.128 to 344.791 confirm the superiority of the extended model over the classical Cox formulation. These findings are consistent with recent studies comparing time-varying coefficient models and alternative approaches such as restricted mean survival time, which also highlight improved model adequacy under non-proportional hazards conditions⁽⁵⁾.

Based on the present analysis, tumor grade emerged as a significant predictor of survival (HR=2.382; 95% CI: 1.653-3433), indicating that increased tumor severity substantially elevates mortality risk. This observation aligns with recent breast cancer survival studies that identify tumor characteristics as key prognostic factors influencing long-term outcomes^{(6), (7), (8)}. However, unlike conventional approaches that assume constant hazard ratios, the current study demonstrates that certain covariates exhibit time-dependent behavior, reinforcing the need for dynamic modeling strategies.

Compared with machine learning-based survival models, such as neural network approaches and random survival forests, previous studies have demonstrated enhanced predictive capability but limited interpretability^{(9), (10), (11), (12)}. In contrast, the extended Cox model used in this study maintains interpretability while effectively capturing time-dependent effects, making it more suitable for clinical applications where understanding covariate effects is essential.

Furthermore, the results support recent developments in stochastic modeling of cancer progression, which emphasize the dynamic and probabilistic nature of survival outcomes^{(13), (14)}. By incorporating time-dependent interactions, the proposed framework provides a more realistic representation of evolving risk patterns in breast cancer patients.

Overall, the findings indicate that reliance on the classical Cox model without testing the PH assumption may lead to oversimplified conclusions. The extended Cox model addresses this limitation by improving both model fit and interpretability, thereby offering a more robust framework for survival analysis.

4 Conclusion

This study tested the proportional hazards assumption in breast cancer data and showed that it often fails for key predictors like age and tumor diameter. Although the classic Cox model picked up significant predictors, it just didn't cut it with time-varying effects. The extended Cox model, adding time-dependent covariates, gave a much better fit. Tumor grade remained a major player, and time-varying covariates revealed how risk truly shifted during follow-up.

This research advances survival analysis by offering a unified framework that integrates testing the proportional hazards assumption with time-dependent modeling. This method improves the precision and understandability of survival models, thereby making it especially valuable for clinical uses.

From a practical perspective, always check the proportional hazards assumption and don't hesitate to use extended models if you spot violations. Future work should look at testing this framework with bigger, multi-center datasets and add the latest in statistical and machine learning techniques.

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About the authors: Mr. S. Vetrivel is a research scholar at Thanthai Periyar Government Arts and Science College (Autonomous), Tiruchirappalli. Dr. S. Sasikala is an associate professor at the same institution.

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